

TITLE: Power Doppler Ultrasound Monitoring of Response to Anti-Tumor Necrosis
Factor Therapy in Patients with Rheumatoid Arthritis

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Abstract

Objective. To evaluate the validity, responsiveness and predictive value of power Doppler (PD) ultrasound (US) monitoring of response to tumor necrosis factor (TNF) blocking agents in rheumatoid arthritis (RA).

Methods. 367 RA patients who started anti-TNF therapy were prospectively recruited in 25 Spanish centers. The patients underwent blinded clinical, laboratory, and PDUS assessment at baseline, 1, 3, 6, and 12 months and radiographic assessment of hands and feet at baseline and 12 months. For each patient, 28-joint Disease Activity Score (DAS28) was recorded at each visit. PDUS examination included 86 intra-articular and periarticular sites in 28 joints. US synovial fluid (SF), synovial hypertrophy (SH) and PD signal were scored in all synovial sites. US count and index for SF, SH, and PD signal were obtained. Sensitivity to change of the PDUS variables was assessed by estimating the smallest detectable difference (SDD) from the intraobserver variability.

Results. A significant parallel improvement in DAS28 and PDUS parameters was found at followup assessments ($p < 0.0005$). The SDD for PDUS parameters was lower than mean changes throughout followup. Time-integrated values (TIV) of US joint count for PD signal and rheumatoid factor (RF) showed predictive values in radiographic erosion score progression ($R = 0.64$). TIV of US joint count for PD signal, RF, and erythrocyte sedimentation rate were predictors of radiographic total score progression ($R = 0.59$).

Conclusion. PDUS is a valid, reproducible and sensitive to change method for monitoring the response to anti-TNF therapy in RA. PDUS findings may have a predictive value in radiologic outcome.

Intra-articular and periarticular synovial inflammation and subsequent structural joint damage are the principal pathological features of rheumatoid arthritis (RA) (1). The accurate monitoring of the response of joint synovitis to RA therapy is essential in daily rheumatological practice and clinical trials. Joint synovitis is widely assessed indirectly by means of inflammatory subjective clinical data and laboratory parameters.

The greater resolution of superficial musculoskeletal structures offered by high-frequency transducers along with the higher sensitivity of current color Doppler (CD) and power Doppler (PD) ultrasound (US) techniques for detecting synovial vascularization have promoted an increasing use of US in rheumatic diseases (2). This technique is a routinely available, non-invasive and relatively inexpensive bedside imaging modality with high patient acceptability which allows the scanning of all peripheral joints as many times as required at the time of consultation.

Within the last decade, US has proved to be more sensitive and reproducible than clinical evaluation in assessing joint inflammation (3-8). There have been an increasing number of studies on the criterion and construct validity of US with CD or PD techniques for evaluating inflammatory activity in RA comparing to histology (9-11), magnetic resonance imaging (12,13) clinical and laboratory parameters (14,15), and radiographic outcome (16,17).

Several longitudinal studies (16,18-24) have described a significant reduction of joint inflammation evaluated by grey-scale and CDUS or PDUS after a variable followup in RA patients treated with tumor necrosis factor (TNF) blocking agents, which have been widely demonstrated to be effective in RA (25-27). These studies have been conducted by individual research centers and have included a small number of patients and/or a reduced number of target RA joints (16,18-24). In addition, most of the

previous studies have not evaluated the sensitivity to change of US parameters.

The purpose of this multicenter long-term study was to demonstrate the validity and responsiveness of a comprehensive PDUS synovitis assessment in monitoring the response to anti-TNF therapy in patients with RA. Furthermore, we investigated the predictive value of PDUS findings in radiological outcome in RA patients who started treatment with anti-TNF agents.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This study prospectively included 367 patients (295 women, 72 men) with RA according to the 1987 American College of Rheumatology (formerly the American Rheumatism Association) criteria for RA (28) who were recruited in the outpatient rheumatologic clinic of 25 Spanish centers from October 2004 to March 2006 and who started therapy with a TNF blocking agent according to Spanish and international consenses on the use of biologic therapy for the treatment of RA (29,30). The mean \pm SD age was 53.7 ± 12.3 years (range 21-85) and mean \pm SD disease duration was 9.1 ± 8.2 years (range 0.5-52). The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the local ethic committees. Informed consent was obtained from all patients before study entry.

The patients underwent a clinical, laboratory, and PDUS evaluation at baseline (within 1 week before starting anti-TNF therapy), 1 month, 3 months, 6 months, and 12 months. Radiographic assessment of patients' hands and feet was performed at baseline and at 12 months of followup. Therapeutic decisions throughout followup were made depending on RA clinical course without knowledge of the PDUS findings.

Clinical and laboratory assessment

The patients underwent a clinical evaluation by the same rheumatologist at each visit (1 rheumatologist in 24 centers, 2 rheumatologists in 1 center), who was blinded to

the PDUS and radiographic findings. The following data were recorded for each patient at study entry: age, sex, symptom duration, disease modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs), and biological agents received for RA before study entry, and rheumatoid factor (RF). Drugs received for RA were recorded at each visit.

At each visit, 28 joints including bilateral glenohumeral, elbow, wrist, metacarpophalangeal (MCP), proximal interphalangeal (PIP) of hands, and knee joints were assessed for tenderness and swelling (31). Tender joint count (TJC) and swollen joint count (SJC) were recorded for each patient. A global pain intensity visual analog scale score (VAS pain; range 0-100 mm), a VAS score for the patient's overall assessment of disease activity (range 0-100 mm) and functional status were also recorded at each visit. Functional ability was evaluated by a self-assessment Spanish version of the Health Assessment Questionnaire (HAQ) (32).

Serum markers of inflammation, C- reactive protein (CRP) level (normal level: 0-10 mg/L) and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) (normal level: 10-20 mm/hour) were obtained from each patient's laboratory test obtained within 48 h of each visit. At study entry and 12 months, RF factor (normal level: 0-15 UI/ml) was also measured for all patient.

Disease activity was estimated by calculating the 28 joint Disease Activity Score (DAS28) for each patient at each visit (33).

PDUS assessment

PDUS assessment was performed for each patient within 4 hours of each clinical evaluation by the same rheumatologist experienced in US (1 rheumatologist in 23 centers, 2 rheumatologists in 2 centers) who was unaware of the clinical, laboratory and radiographic findings and who was not involved in the treatment decisions. To reduce the possibility of bias, PDUS was carried out without access to the previous visit results. The

patients were asked not to talk about their clinical symptoms with the US examiner. The PDUS examination was performed in a darkened room.

A systematic multiplanar grey-scale and PDUS examination of the 28 joints clinically investigated was carried out with commercially available real-time scanners (Logiq 5 PRO, General Electric Healthcare, Kyunnggi-do, Korea, in 23 centers and Logiq 7, General Electric Healthcare, Tokio, Japan, in 2 centers) using multifrequency linear array transducers, 7-12 MHz. The 28-joint PDUS assessment included the investigation of intra-articular synovitis, tenosynovitis, bursitis, and synovial PD signal in 86 anatomic sites (Table 1).

US scanning technique, grey-scale and PD machine settings, and pathology definitions were standardized among investigators prior to the study. The US scanning method has been described in previous published studies (5,10,15,17,34,35). Synovitis, tenosynovitis, and bursitis were defined according to the OMERACT definitions and published descriptions (15,17,36,37).

Synovial fluid (SF) and synovial hypertrophy (SH) within intra-articular recesses, tendon synovial sheaths and bursae were graded semiquantitatively from 0 to 3 (0=absence; 1=mild, 2=moderate; 3=marked) during the grey-scale US examination.

Synovial, tenosynovial and intrabursal blood flow was evaluated by PD at each joint. PD imaging was performed by selecting a region of interest that included the bony margins, synovial site, and a variable view of surrounding tissues. Pulse repetition frequency (PRF) was adjusted at the lowest permissible value to maximise sensitivity. This setting resulted in PRF ranging from 500 to 750 Hz depending on the anatomic area scanned. Low wall filters were used. The dynamic range was 20-40 dB. Color gain was set just below the level at which color noise appeared underlying bone (no flow should be visualized at bony surface) This setting resulted in gains from 18 dB to 30 dB.

Flow was additionally demonstrated in 2 planes and confirmed by pulsed-wave Doppler spectrum to exclude artifacts.

The intra-articular, tenosynovial and intrabursal PD signal was graded on a semiquantitative scale from 0 to 3 (0=absence, no synovial flow; 1=mild, 3 or less isolated signals; 2=moderate, more than 3 isolated signals or confluent signal in less than half of the synovial area; 3=marked, signals in more than half of the synovial area) during the PDUS examination.

A score for SF, SH, and PD signal (0-3) was assigned to each joint corresponding to the maximum scores obtained from the synovial sites evaluated at each of them.

A count for joints with SF (USCSF), a count for joints with SH (USCSH), and a count for joints with PD signal (USCPD) in any synovial site were obtained at each visit.

An overall joint index for SF (USISF), an overall joint index for SH (USISH), and an overall joint index for PD signal (USIPD) (the sum of the SF, SH and PD signal scores, respectively, obtained from each joint) were calculated at each PDUS assessment.

PDUS intraobserver reliability

Intraobserver reliability of the PDUS assessment was evaluated by recording representative images of the full baseline examination of 150 patients included in the study from all centers. The stored images of each patient were blindly scored for SF, SH and PD signal by the same investigator who performed the corresponding real-time PDUS examination a minimum of 3 months later.

PDUS interobserver reliability

Interobserver reliability between US investigators was evaluated before patients' inclusion by scoring for SF, SH and PD signal images of the joints included in the PDUS assessment from 20 active RA patients, randomly chosen by the investigator who coordinated the study (EN).

Radiographic assessment

Postero-anterior films of patients' hands and antero-posterior films of patients' feet were made at baseline (within 10 days of study entry) and at 12 months of followup. The radiographs were read twice with a minimum interval of 2 weeks, in chronological order by an independent observer (AC) who was blinded to patients' identity and clinical, laboratory, and PDUS findings. Radiologic damage was assessed according to van der Heijde and colleagues' modification of Sharp's method (38,39). This method measures erosions (score range 0-280) and joint space narrowing (JSN) (score range 0-168) in 44 different joints, and provides a sum score ranging from 0 to 448. As defined in the description of the scoring method, total scores could increase or be stable, but could not decrease. Results were expressed as erosion score, JSN score, and total score.

Scores from the first assessment of baseline and final films were used for analysis with the clinical, laboratory, and PDUS data. Intraobserver reliability was assessed by calculating the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) from both radiographic readings.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS statistical software, version 13.0 (SPSS, Chicago, IL). Quantitative variables (clinical, laboratory, PDUS, and radiographic parameters, and DAS28) were given as the mean \pm SD and range. Repeated measures ANOVA and pairwise comparison with repeated contrast between

adjacent categories within successive visits was used for comparing quantitative variables throughout followup. Modified US disease activity scores (USDAS28) were calculated for all patients at each visit replacing the SJC of the DAS28 by USCSF (USDAS28SF), USCSH (USDAS28SH), and USCPD (USDAS28PD). Correlations between clinical, laboratory, DAS28, USDAS28, PDUS, and radiographic parameters were analyzed by Pearson's correlation test. The course of the process variables was obtained by calculating time-integrated values (TIV) using the area under the curve method (40).

Intraobserver reliability of the PDUS and radiographic parameters was evaluated by calculating the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) (2-way mixed effects). Sensitivity to change of the PDUS and radiographic variables was assessed by estimating the smallest detectable difference (SDD) (41,42).

PDUS interobserver variability was evaluated using the Kendall's W test. A Kendall's W value < 0.40 was considered poor, 0.40-0.50 moderate, 0.50-0.70 good and 0.70-1 excellent.

Multivariate regression models were used to predict radiological progression at 12 months from baseline and cumulative clinical, laboratory, and PDUS variables.

Any p value less 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Patient characteristics

Complete clinical, laboratory and PDUS data were obtained from 278 patients (227 women, 51 men) who had received TB for a minimum of 10 months throughout followup. The mean \pm SD age was 53.3 ± 12.2 years (range 22-85) and mean \pm SD disease duration was 9.6 ± 8.2 years (range 0.5-52). Rheumatoid factor was positive in 219 (78.8%) patients. Before study entry, 36 patients (12.9%) had received 1 DMARD,

and 242 (87.1 %) patients had received more than 1 DMARDs. Forty-two (15.1%) patients had received one previous biological agent and 10 patients (3.6%) had received 2 previous biological agents. These patients had been switched to another TNF blocking agent because of ineffectiveness (80.7%) or adverse effects (19.2%).

At inclusion, 203 (73%) patients were taking methotrexate, 64 (23%) leflunomide and 11 (3.9%) other DMARDs. Sixty-seven (24.1%) patients were taking more than 1 DMARD. Two hundred twenty-one (79.5%) patients received prednisone and 235 (84.5%) patients received nonsteroidal antiinflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). Two hundred fifty-three (91%) patients started therapy with adalimumab, 16 (5.8%) patients with etanercept, and 9 (3.2%) patients with infliximab. Twenty-four (8.6%) patients were switched to another anti-TNF agent during followup mainly because of ineffectiveness (54.1%) or adverse effects (25%).

Clinical, laboratory, PDUS, and radiographic course

Clinical, laboratory, and PDUS parameters during followup are given in Table 2. A significant parallel decrease in all clinical, functional and PDUS parameters was found at followup assessments ($p < 0.0005$ for each parameter). The mean ESR value fell significantly from baseline to 1 month and from 3 months to 6 months. The mean CRP value decreased significantly from baseline to 1 month. There was a parallel decrease in DAS28 and modified USDAS28 with SF, SH and PD throughout followup. There was a highly significant correlation between changes in the DAS28 and changes in the USDAS28SF, USDAS28SH, and USDAS28PD (Pearson's $r > 0.94$, $p < 0.01$) throughout the study (Figure 1). Representative images of PDUS changes in a MCP joint after anti-TNF therapy are shown in Figure 2.

Baseline and final radiographs were available from 164 patients. The mean \pm SD total radiographic score increase from 74.2 ± 74.8 (range 1-355) at study entry to 87.9

± 79.3 (range 2-366) at 12 months. One hundred fifty-nine (97%) patients showed progression in total radiographic score (mean \pm SD, 13.68 ± 14.16), 132 (80.4 %) patients in erosion score (mean \pm SD, 7.0 ± 8.3), and 154 (93.9 %) patients in JSN score (mean \pm SD, 8.6 ± 7.7) at 12 months of followup.

Intraobserver reliability and sensitivity to change of the PDUS assessment

Table 3 displays the intraobserver ICCs for the PDUS variables. All ICCs were significant at level of $p < 0.001$. We obtained a high intraobserver reliability. Throughout followup, the changes in the PDUS parameters were higher than their SDD (Table 3).

Intraobserver reliability and sensitivity to change of the radiographic assessment

ICCs for the baseline films were 0.99 (95% confidence interval (CI)) 0.98-0.99) for the erosion score, 0.98 (95% CI 0.97-0.98) for the JSN score, and 0.99 (95% CI 0.99- 0.99) for the total score. ICCs for the films taken after 12 months were 0.99 (95% CI 0.98-0.99) for the erosion score, 0.97 (95% CI 0.96-0.99) for the JSN score, and 0.99 (95% CI 0.98-0.99) for the total score. The SDDs were 2.07 for the erosion score, 2.27 for the JSN score, and 2.92 for the total score. The changes in the erosion score (mean \pm SD, 5.64 ± 7.91), JSN score (mean \pm SD, 8.04 ± 7.72), and total score (mean \pm SD, 13.68 ± 14.16) were higher than their SDD.

Predictive value of clinical, laboratory, and PDUS variables in radiologic outcome at 12 months

Multivariate regression models revealed that among all clinical, laboratory, and PDUS variables, the TIV of USCPD and RF were predictors of radiographic erosion score progression ($R = 0.64$) and the TIV of USCPD, RF, and ESR were predictors of radiographic total score progression ($R = 0.59$) (Table 4). There was a weaker predictive value of cumulative RF and CRP in JSN score progression ($R = 0.38$). Baseline RF

value resulted predictor of erosion ($R= 0.42$) and total score progression ($R= 0.34$), and baseline CRP level showed a weak predictive value in JSN score progression ($R= 0.2$), (Table 4).

Interobserver reliability of the PDUS assessment

Interobserver agreement was significant for SF, SH and PD signal ($p < 0.05$). Kendall' W coefficient was 0.64 for SF and SH and 0.85 for PD signal.

Discussion

Over the past few years, there has been an increasing use of musculoskeletal US with CD or PD techniques for detecting and monitoring joint inflammatory activity in patients with RA (2,43,44).

For this study, a large cohort of RA patients who started anti-TNF agents was investigated longitudinally. We assessed with PDUS the 28 joints included in the DAS28 (33) as a comprehensive method for evaluating overall RA inflammatory activity. We chose a combination of grey scale and PD findings as imaging variables reflecting rheumatoid joint inflammation. In addition, as reported by Iagnocco et al (23,24), we included periarticular inflammatory findings in the PDUS assessment.

We found a significant improvement in PDUS parameters parallel to changes in clinical and laboratory indices of disease activity throughout the followup. When we replaced SJC of the DAS28 by PDUS variables of joint inflammation, changes in modified USDAS28 values were parallel to and showed a highly significant correlation with changes in DAS28. These results demonstrate construct validity of the PDUS longitudinal assessment of rheumatoid synovial inflammation.

Our results were in agreement with those of previous longitudinal studies that have shown changes in CDUS or PDUS findings associated with clinical and laboratory response to TNF blocking agents in RA patients (16,18-24). Most of them have

evaluated few patients (18,19,20,21,23) and/or a few joints (18,20,21,22) and/or during a short followup (18,19). These facts have probably limited the investigation of responsiveness and predictive value of US findings in RA patients treated with anti-TNF agents.

The sensitivity to change of any method should be demonstrated by calculating the intraobserver variation and the SDD between repeated measurements (45). Most of the previous longitudinal studies have not assessed the sensitivity to change of US parameters (16,18,20,22,23,24). Ribbens et al (19) and Fiocco et al (21) reported intraobserver coefficients of variation lower than the changes in PD findings induced by anti-TNF therapy in RA patients. We obtained a lower SDD for the PDUS parameters than the changes in these variables from baseline to 1 month, 3 months, 6 months, and 12 months. Therefore, responsiveness of the PDUS assessment has also been proved in this study.

Cumulative count for joints with PD signal along with RF and laboratory markers for inflammation, CRP and ESR were predictors of radiologic damage progression in our study. The predictive value of RF, CRP, and ESR in radiologic damage and progression in RA has been widely reported (46-48). In keeping with Taylor et al (16), we did not find relationship between baseline synovial PD signal and radiologic joint damage progression in patients receiving anti-TNF therapy. In a previous study (17), we demonstrated the predictive value of cumulative joint count for synovial PD signal in radiologic progression in patients with early RA who started therapy with DMARDs. Radiological joint damage in RA is considered the consequence of persistent inflammatory activity (49). Our results can reflect the pathogenic destructive role of persistent synovial angiogenesis and hypervascularization in the rheumatoid joint (50). Therefore, the finding of synovial PD signal in rheumatoid

joints may be considered a measurement of response to anti-TNF therapy independent of clinical and grey-scale US indices of disease activity in RA.

In spite of the high number of US examiners, the interobserver reliability was good for SF and SH and excellent for PD signal. It is likely that the strict standardization of scanning method and pathology definitions conducted before the study began contributed to reduce interobserver variability between investigators.

Some limitations of our study should be mentioned. With regard to intraobserver and interobserver reliability, image acquisition variability was not investigated. The assessment of selected PDUS images instead of the real time examination of the joints obviously introduces bias into the study. In addition, PDUS interobserver reliability was assessed in a relatively low number of patients. However, testing intraobserver acquisition reliability would have been problematic for patients because of the extensive PDUS examination. Testing interobserver acquisition reliability was not considered due to the number of investigators involved in the study.

This study was conducted in accordance with daily clinical practice. In addition to anti-TNF agents, patients were treated with various DMARDs, oral corticosteroids and NSAIDs at a variable dose during the study. These differences in treatment could introduce bias into the study. However, since anti-TNF therapy was indicated because RA was active despite treatment with DMARDs, prednisone, and NSAIDs, it may be accepted that changes in clinical and PDUS parameters were due mainly to anti-TNF agents.

In conclusion, our results provide evidence of contrast validity and responsiveness of PDUS monitoring of the response of RA joint inflammatory activity to anti-TNF therapy in this multicenter study. Furthermore, the presence of synovial PD signal seems to have a predictive value in radiologic progression in established RA treated with anti-TNF agents.

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Table 1. Synovial intra-articular recesses and periarticular sites evaluated at each joint by power Doppler ultrasound

Joints (bilateral)	Synovial sites
Shoulder	Posterior recess
	Axillar recess
	Biceps tendon sheath
	Subdeltoid bursa
Elbow	Anterior recess
	Posterior recess
Wrist	Dorsal carpal recesses
	Volar carpal recesses
	Extensor tendon sheaths
	Flexor tendon sheaths
Knee	Suprapatellar recess
	Medial parapatellar recess
	Lateral parapatellar recess
MCP and PIP of hands	Dorsal recess
	Palmar recess
	Flexor tendons sheath

MCP, metacarpophalangeal; PIP, proximal interphalangeal

Table 2. Clinical, laboratory, and PDUS parameters at followup assessments

	Baseline (mean ± SD)	1 month (mean ± SD)	3 month (mean ± SD)	6 month (mean ± SD)	12 month (mean ± SD)
VASP	59.9 ± 23.7	38.5 ± 23.8 §	36.3 ± 25	33.3 ± 22.6 †	29 ± 23.4 ‡
VASOA	60 ± 24.3	37.4 ± 22.9 §	35 ± 24.5 †	33.2 ± 22.6	29.1 ± 22.4 ‡
TJC	11 ± 6.2	6.3 ± 4.9 §	5.6 ± 5.2 ‡	4.4 ± 4.6 §	3.8 ± 4.9 †
SJC	9 ± 4.8	5.3 ± 4.1 §	4.8 ± 4	3.7 ± 3.5 §	3.4 ± 3.8
ESR	36.1 ± 20.5	26.3 ± 17.9 §	27 ± 19.4	24.3 ± 17.5 §	24.7 ± 17.8
CRP	16.3 ± 24.5	7.2 ± 12.3 §	8.1 ± 15.7	6.5 ± 10.3	6.7 ± 10.7
HAQ	1.47 ± 0.66	1.07 ± 0.67 §	0.95 ± 0.67 §	0.89 ± 0.66 †	0.83 ± 0.65
DAS28	5.69 ± 1.01	4.52 ± 1.22 §	4.31 ± 1.32 ‡	3.95 ± 1.21 §	3.73 ± 1.31 ‡
USCSF	11.3 ± 5.8	8.4 ± 5.6 §	7.5 ± 5.7 ‡	6.5 ± 5.2 §	6.2 ± 5.5
USCSH	11.5 ± 6.2	8.8 ± 6 §	7.8 ± 5.9 §	6.9 ± 5.8 §	6.6 ± 5.8
USCPD	6.6 ± 4.8	4.2 ± 3.6 §	3.8 ± 3.9 †	3 ± 3.5 §	2.9 ± 3.5
USISF	15.6 ± 9.9	10.8 ± 8.3 §	9.5 ± 8.1 ‡	8.1 ± 7.2 §	8 ± 8
USISH	16.4 ± 10.5	11.5 ± 8.9 §	10.4 ± 8.7 ‡	9 ± 8.3 §	8.5 ± 8.6
USIPD	9 ± 7.2	5.5 ± 5.5 §	5.3 ± 6.1	4.1 ± 5.3 §	3.8 ± 5
RF	200.7 ± 451				152.9 ± 315.4 †

All ANOVA within subjects were significant at level $p < 0.0005$. Planned pairwise comparison with the preceding visit: † $p < 0.05$; ‡ $p < 0.01$; § $p < 0.001$

PDUS, power Doppler ultrasound; VASP, visual analog scale for pain; VASOA, visual analog scale for patient's overall assessment of disease activity; TCJ, tender joint count; SJC, swollen joint count; ESR, erythrocyte sedimentation rate; CRP, C- reactive

protein; HAQ, Health Assessment Questionnaire; DAS 28, 28 joint Disease Activity Score; USCSF, ultrasound joint count for synovial fluid; USCSH, ultrasound joint count for synovial hypertrophy; USCPD, ultrasound joint count for PD signal; USISF, ultrasound joint index for synovial fluid; USISH, ultrasound joint index for synovial hypertrophy; USIPD, ultrasound joint index for PD signal.

Table 3. Intraobserver reliability and sensitivity to change of the PDUS parameters

	Intraobserver ICC (95% CI)	SDD	Mean change (95% CI) baseline-1 month	Mean change (95% CI) baseline-3 month	Mean change (95% CI) baseline-6 month	Mean change (95% CI) baseline-12 month
USCSF	0.961 (0.947-0.972)	1.27	2.9 (2.2-3.4)	3.8 (3.2-4.5)	4.8 (4.2-5.5)	5.1 (4.3-5.8)
USCSH	0.956 (0.940-0.968)	0.93	2.7 (2.2-3.3)	3.6 (3-4.3)	4.6 (3.9-5.3)	4.9 (4.2.-5.7)
USCPD	0.958 (0.943-0.970)	0.80	2.4 (2.1-3)	2.8 (2.3-3.4)	3.6 (3.1-4.2)	3.7 (3.1-4.2)
USISF	0.967 (0.954-0.976)	2.23	4.7 (3.8-5.6)	6.1 (5.1-7)	7.4 (6.4-8.4)	7.6 (6.4-8.8)
USISH	0.957 (0.941-0.968)	1.93	4.8 (3.9-5.7)	6 (5-7.1)	7.3 (6-8.5)	8 (6.7-9.2)
USIPD	0.968 (0.956-0.976)	0.82	3.5 (2.9-4.2)	3.8 (3-4.5)	4.9 (4.1-5.7)	5.1 (4.3-5.9)

PDUS, power Doppler ultrasound; ICC, intraclass correlation coefficient; CI, confidence interval; SDD, smallest detectable difference; USCSF, ultrasound joint count for synovial fluid; USCSH, ultrasound joint count for synovial hypertrophy; USCPD, ultrasound joint count for PD signal; USISF, ultrasound joint index for synovial fluid; USISH, ultrasound joint index for synovial hypertrophy; USIPD, ultrasound joint index for PD signal.

Table 4. Predictive value of baseline and time-integrated variables in radiologic progression

		Dependent variable		
		Erosion score progression	JSN progression	Total score progression
Baseline independent variables	Multiple R	0.422	0.204	0.341
	Adjusted R squared	0.166	0.034	0.103
	variables	B coefficients significant at level 0.05		
	RF	0.0020		0.011
	CRP		0.051	
	Constant	4.9837	6.946	8.4408
Time integrated independent variables	Multiple R	0.638	0.380	0.588
	Adjusted R squared	0.396	0.129	0.328
	variables	B coefficients significant at level 0.05		
	RF	0.0004	0.0001	0.0005
	USCPD	0.0012		0.0022
	CRP		0.0006	
	ESR			0.0004
	Constant	1.4731	5.933	3.5692

R, multiple correlation coefficient; JSN, joint space narrowing; RF, rheumatoid factor; CRP, C- reactive protein; USCPD, ultrasound joint count for PD signal, ESR, erythrocyte sedimentation rate .

Figures

Figure 1. Changes in DAS28 and modified ultrasonographic DAS28 with synovial fluid, synovial hypertrophy and power Doppler signal throughout followup

DAS 28, 28 joint Disease Activity Score; USDAS28SF, ultrasound DAS28 with synovial fluid; USDAS28SH, ultrasound DAS28 with synovial hypertrophy; USDAS28PD, ultrasound DAS28 with power Doppler signal.

Figure 2. Longitudinal ultrasound image of a metacarpophalangeal joint at baseline (Figure 2a) and at 1 month of anti-TNF therapy (Figure 2b). Figure 2a shows moderate synovial fluid, synovial hypertrophy and synovial power Doppler signal whereas Figure 2b shows a normal joint without the previous pathological findings. mc, metacarpal bone; pp, proximal phalanx.

